

ON DIRECTION DEPENDENT COMPLEX MANIFOLDS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the authors have defined a new set of connection coefficients which gives rise to a new process of a covariant differentiation. Based over this new covariant differentiation two distinct curvature tensors along with their starred counterpart are found. Various relations among these curvature tensors and the curvature tensors already existing, have been found.

Keywords: Covariant differentiation, curvature tensors, holomorphic functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rund (1967), defined a complex manifold C_n , which can be regarded as generalization of Hermitian or Kahler space in a sense which is analogous to the transition from Riemannian to Finsler geometry. In this paper, we will define a connection coefficient and use it to define a new covariant differentiation. With the help of this covariant differentiation, we will get two curvature tensors and establish relations between these and the existing curvature tensors due to Rund (1972) and Oosthuizen (1972). Notations used are of Rund (1967).

Let C_n be a n -dimensional complex manifold referred to the complex coordinates (z^j, z^{j*}) . [Here, and in the sequel, all Latin indices j, h, k, \dots range from 1 to n]. The laws of transformation of coordinates are given by

$$\bar{z}^j = \bar{z}^j(z^k), \bar{z}^{j*} = z^{j*}(z^{k*}), \det \left(\frac{\partial \bar{z}^j}{\partial z^k} \right) \neq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

where \bar{z}^j and \bar{z}^{j*} are holomorphic function of z^k and z^{k*} respectively. We use the following notations

$$\frac{\partial \bar{z}^j}{\partial z^h} = A_h^j(z^k), \frac{\partial \bar{z}^{j*}}{\partial z^{h*}} = A_h^{j*}(z^{k*}),$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{z}^j}{\partial z^h \partial z^k} = A_{hk}^j(z^l) \quad (1.2)$$

Together

$$\frac{\partial z^h}{\partial \bar{z}^j} = B_j^h(z^k), \frac{\partial z^{h*}}{\partial \bar{z}^{j*}} = B_j^{h*}(z^{k*}),$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 z^h}{\partial \bar{z}^j \partial \bar{z}^k} = B_{jk}^h(z^l) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial^3 z^h}{\partial \bar{z}^j \partial \bar{z}^k \partial \bar{z}^m} = B_{jkm}^h(z^l)$$

The transformation laws of directional arguments are given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z^m} = B_m^l \frac{\partial}{\partial z^l}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z^{m*}} = B_m^{l*} \frac{\partial}{\partial z^{l*}}$$

so that

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \bar{z}^m} = B_m^l, \frac{\partial z}{\partial \bar{z}^{m*}} = 0, \frac{\partial z}{\partial \bar{z}^m} = B_m^{l*}, \frac{\partial z}{\partial \bar{z}^k} = B_{mk}^l, \frac{\partial z}{\partial \bar{z}^h} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial z^i}{\partial z^{\bar{k}}} = B_{m^*k}^{l^*} z^{\bar{m}^*}$$

It is assumed that the space C_n is endowed with a set of differentiable connection coefficient

$$\Gamma_{jk}^h \left(z^j, z^{\bar{j}^*}, z, z^{\bar{j}^*} \right) \text{ and } \Gamma_{j^*k^*}^{h^*} \left(z^j, z^{\bar{j}^*}, z, z^{\bar{j}^*} \right)$$

which satisfy the customary transformation laws.

$$B_{mk}^l = B_t^l \bar{\Gamma}_{mk}^t - B_m^p B_k^h \Gamma_{ph}^l \quad (1.6 a)$$

and

$$B_{m^*k^*}^{l^*} = B_t^{l^*} \bar{\Gamma}_{m^*k^*}^{t^*} - B_m^{p^*} B_{k^*}^{h^*} \Gamma_{p^*h^*}^{l^*} \quad (1.6 b)$$

under the coordinate transformation (1.1).

Let $T_{mn}^{jh^*}(z^j, z^{\bar{j}^*}, \dot{z}^j, \dot{z}^{\bar{j}^*})$ be an arbitrary tensor of contra-variant valency (1+1) and covariant valency (1+1) and I and II denote the covariant differentiations defined by Rund (1972) and Oosthuizen (1972) respectively, then we have

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_k = \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_k^l + T_{mn}^{ph^*} \Gamma_{pk}^j - T_{pn}^{jh^*} \Gamma_{mk}^p \quad (1.7 a)$$

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_{k^*} = \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^{k^*}} - \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^{l^*}} \Gamma_{k^*}^{l^*} + T_{mn}^{jp^*} \Gamma_{p^*k^*}^{h^*} - T_{mp}^{jh^*} \Gamma_{n^*k^*}^{p^*} \quad (1.7 b)$$

and

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_{||k} = \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_k^l + T_{mn}^{ph^*} \Gamma_{kp}^j - T_{pn}^{jh^*} \Gamma_{km}^p \quad (1.8 a)$$

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_{||k^*} = \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^{k^*}} - \frac{\partial T_{mn}^{jh^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^{l^*}} \Gamma_{k^*}^{l^*} + T_{mn}^{jp^*} \Gamma_{k^*p^*}^{h^*} - T_{mp}^{jh^*} \Gamma_{k^*n^*}^{p^*} \quad (1.8 b)$$

Where we have written

$$\Gamma_k^l = \Gamma_{jk}^l \dot{z}^j, \quad \Gamma_{k^*}^{l^*} = \Gamma_{j^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{j^*}, \quad (1.9)$$

These two covariant derivatives are related by:

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_k - T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_{||k} = T_{mn}^{ph^*} \Omega_{pk}^j - T_{pn}^{jh^*} \Omega_{mk}^p \quad (1.10)$$

and

$$T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_k - T_{mn}^{jh^*}|_{||k^*} = T_{mn}^{jp^*} \Omega_{p^*k^*}^{h^*} - T_{mp}^{jh^*} \Omega_{n^*k^*}^{p^*} \quad (1.11)$$

where

$$\Omega_{pk}^j = \Gamma_{pk}^j - \Gamma_{kp}^j, \quad \Omega_{p^*k^*}^{j^*} = \Gamma_{p^*k^*}^{j^*} - \Gamma_{k^*p^*}^{j^*}, \quad (1.12)$$

In C_n Rund (1972) has defined two curvature tensors as follows:

$$K_{mhh^*}^j = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{mh}^j}{\partial z^{k^*}} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{mh}^j}{\partial \dot{z}^{l^*}} \Gamma_k^{l^*} \quad (1.13)$$

$$K_{hkm}^j = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{hk}^j}{\partial z^m} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{hk}^j}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_m^l - \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{hm}^j}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{hm}^j}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_k^l \right) \quad (1.14)$$

$$+ \Gamma_{pm}^j \Gamma_{hk}^p - \Gamma_{pk}^j \Gamma_{hm}^p$$

Alongwith their starred counterparts.

Afterwards Oosthuizen(1972) obtained one more curvature tensor

$$\bar{K}_{hkm}^j = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{kh}^j}{\partial z^m} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{kh}^j}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_m^l - \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{mh}^j}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{mh}^j}{\partial \dot{z}^l} \Gamma_k^l \right) \quad (1.15)$$

$$+ \Gamma_{mp}^j \Gamma_{kh}^p - \Gamma_{pk}^j \Gamma_{mh}^p$$

alongwith its starred counterpart $\bar{K}_{h^*k^*m^*}^{j^*}$ and showed that a relation between K_{hkm}^j and \bar{K}_{hkm}^j exist, although the tensors given by Rund are independent. The identity.

$$K_{mhh^*}^j - K_{hmk^*}^j = \Omega_{mh|k}^j \quad (1.16)$$

will be found useful in the onward discussion.

2. COVARIANT DIFFERENTIATION

In this article, we will define a covariant differentiation operation based on the connection coefficients γ_{jk}^h and

$\Lambda_{j^*k^*}^{h^*}$ obtained from the symmetric part of Γ_{jk}^h and $\Gamma_{j^*k^*}^{h^*}$ respectively.

we put

$$\gamma_k^h = \frac{1}{2}(\Gamma_{jk}^h + \Gamma_{kj}^h) \tag{2.1 a}$$

$$\Lambda_{j^*k^*}^{h^*} = \frac{1}{2}(\Gamma_{j^*k^*}^{h^*} + \Gamma_{k^*j^*}^{h^*}) \tag{2.1 b}$$

then from equation (1.6) (a) and (1.6) (b), we immediately find

$$B_{mk}^l = B_t^l \bar{\Lambda}_{mk}^t - B_m^p B_k^h \Lambda_{ph}^l \tag{2.2}$$

together with its starred counterpart, which show that the entities Λ_{jk}^h and $\Lambda_{j^*k^*}^{h^*}$ satisfy the transformation laws of the connection coefficients and hence can be used to define a new covariant differentiation process, which we will be denoted by semicolon (;). Thus we define

$$T_{mn^*;k}^{jh^*} = \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^l} \Lambda_{tk}^l \dot{z}^t + T_{mn^*}^{ph^*} \Lambda_{pk}^j - T_{pn^*}^{jh^*} \Lambda_{mk}^p \tag{2.3}$$

and

$$T_{mn^*i^*k^*}^{jh^*} = \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^l} \Lambda_{i^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{i^*} + T_{mn^*p^*k^*}^{jp^*h^*} - T_{mp^*n^*k^*}^{jh^*p^*} \tag{2.4}$$

In particular, we find that if a tensor $T(z, z^*, z^*)$ possesses only starred indices, one has

$$T_{n^*k^*}^{h^*} = \frac{\partial T_{n^*}^{h^*}}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial T_{n^*}^{h^*}}{\partial z^l} \Lambda_{ik^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{i^*}$$

and if $S(z, z^*, z^*)$ be a tensor with only unstarred indices, then

$$S_{h^*k^*}^j = \frac{\partial S_h^j}{\partial z^k} - \frac{\partial S_h^j}{\partial z^l} \Lambda_{i^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{i^*}$$

From these two relations, we infer the following "If a tensor possesses only starred {unstarred} indices and is holomorphic function of $(z^k, \dot{z}^k), \{(z^{k^*}, \dot{z}^{k^*})\}$, then its covariant derivative with respect to $z^k \{z^{k^*}\}$ vanishes identically."

By straight forward calculations, we have the following equations

$$T_{mn^*k}^{jh^*} = T_{mn^*|k}^{jh^*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^l} \Omega_{tk}^l \dot{z}^t + \frac{1}{2} T_{mn^*}^{ph^*} \Omega_{kp}^j - \frac{1}{2} T_{pn^*}^{jh^*} \Omega_{km}^p \tag{2.5}$$

$$T_{mn^*i^*k^*}^{jh^*} = T_{mn^*|k^*}^{jh^*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^{l^*}} \Omega_{t^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{t^*} + \frac{1}{2} T_{mn^*}^{jp^*} \Omega_{k^*p^*}^{h^*} - \frac{1}{2} T_{mp^*}^{jh^*} \Omega_{k^*n^*}^{p^*} \tag{2.6}$$

$$T_{mn^*i^*k^*}^{jh^*} = T_{mn^*||k^*}^{jh^*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^{l^*}} \Omega_{t^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{t^*} + \frac{1}{2} T_{mn^*}^{ph^*} \Omega_{kp}^j - \frac{1}{2} T_{pn^*}^{jh^*} \Omega_{mk}^p \tag{2.7}$$

$$T_{mn^*i^*k^*}^{jh^*} = T_{mn^*||k^*}^{jh^*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial T_{mn^*}^{jh^*}}{\partial z^{l^*}} \Omega_{t^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{t^*} + \frac{1}{2} T_{mn^*}^{jp^*} \Omega_{p^*k^*}^{h^*} - \frac{1}{2} T_{mp^*}^{jh^*} \Omega_{n^*k^*}^{p^*} \tag{2.8}$$

Analogous to the geometric entities Γ_k^l and $\Gamma_{k^*}^{l^*}$, we define

$$\Lambda_k^l = \Lambda_{hk}^l \dot{z}^h \tag{2.9 a}$$

$$\Lambda_{k^*}^{l^*} = \Lambda_{h^*k^*}^{l^*} \dot{z}^{h^*} \tag{2.9 b}$$

now, multiplying (2.2) by \dot{z}^m , using (2.9) (a), (1.4) and (1.5) we get

$$\frac{\partial \dot{z}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^k} = B_t^l \bar{\Lambda}_k^t - B_k^h \Lambda_h^l \tag{2.10}$$

A similar calculation, with the help of (2.2), (2.9) (b), (1.4) and (1.5) yields.

$$\frac{\partial \dot{z}^{l^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^{k^*}} = B_{t^*}^{l^*} \bar{\Lambda}_{k^*}^{t^*} - B_{k^*}^{h^*} \Lambda_{h^*}^{l^*} \tag{2.11}$$

3. CURVATURE TENSORS

Since the preceding theory is independent of the metric of the space, the following theory of curvature is also valid for any differentiable manifold endowed with a complex structure.

Here we will derive the curvature tensors by means of an investigation of the integrability conditions of the transformation laws of connection coefficients λ_{hk}^j and

$$\lambda_{h^*k^*}^{j^*}$$

Differentiating the transformation law (2.2) with respect to \dot{z}^r and multiplying the equation thus obtained by B_n^r we get

$$B_t^l \frac{\partial \bar{\lambda}_{mk}^t}{\partial \dot{z}^n} = B_m^p B_k^h \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^r} \quad (3.1)$$

Similarly, if we differentiate (2.2) with respect to \dot{z}^{r^*} and multiply the equation thus obtained by $B_n^{r^*}$ we get

$$B_t^l \frac{\partial \bar{\lambda}_{mk}^t}{\partial \dot{z}^{n^*}} = B_m^p B_k^h B_n^{r^*} \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^{r^*}} \quad (3.2)$$

The above two equations show that the directional derivatives of our connection coefficients are tensorial in character. These equations are to be used in further analysis.

Now, differentiating (2.2) with respect to \bar{z}^{r^*} and substituting for $\frac{\partial \dot{z}^l}{\partial \bar{z}^{k^*}}$ from (2.11) in the equation thus obtained, we get with the help of (3.2)

$$B_t^l \bar{H}_{mkr^*}^t = B_m^p B_k^h B_r^{n^*} H_{phn}^l \quad (3.3)$$

where we have p

$$H_{mkr^*}^t = \frac{\partial \lambda_{mk}^t}{\partial z^{r^*}} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{mk}^t}{\partial z^s} \lambda_r^{s^*} \quad (3.4)$$

Equation (3.3) shows that $H_{mkr^*}^t$ defined by (3.4) are components of a tensor of contravariant valency (1+0) and covariant valency (2+1), We shall call this tensors as First curvature tensor depending on the symmetric connection

$$\lambda_{hk}^j$$

On the other hand, differentiation (2.2) with respect to z^r and making use of (1.3), we find:

$$B_{mkr}^l = B_{tr}^l \bar{\lambda}_{mh}^t + B_t^l \frac{\partial \bar{\lambda}_{mk}^t}{\partial \bar{z}^r} - B_{mr}^p B_k^h \lambda_{ph}^l - B_m^p B_{kr}^h \lambda_{ph}^l -$$

$$B_m^p B_k^h \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial z^s} B_r^s + \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial z^s} \frac{\partial z^s}{\partial \bar{z}^r} \right)$$

which in view of (2.2), (2.10) and (3.1) reduces to the form

$$B_{mkr}^l = B_t^l \left[\frac{\partial \bar{\lambda}_{mh}^t}{\partial \bar{z}^r} - \frac{\partial \bar{\lambda}_{mk}^t}{\partial \dot{z}^s} \bar{\lambda}_r^s + \bar{\lambda}_{sr}^t \bar{\lambda}_{mk}^s \right] -$$

$$B_m^p B_k^h B_r^s \left[\frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial z^s} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^g} \lambda_s^g - \lambda_{th}^l \lambda_{ph}^t \right]$$

$$- B_d^p \lambda_{ph}^l \left[B_k^h \lambda_{mr}^{-d} + B_r^h \lambda_{mk}^{-d} \right] -$$

$$B_m^p \lambda_{ph}^l \left[B_a^h \bar{\lambda}_{kr}^{-a} - B_k^b B_r^c \lambda_{bc}^h \right]$$

As the expression on left hand side is symmetric in all its lower indices, so applying these symmetry conditions in the equation (3.5), we find

$$B_t^l \bar{H}_{mkr}^t = B_m^p B_k^h B_r^s H_{phs}^l \quad (3.6)$$

where we have put

$$H_{phs}^l = \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial z^s} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^g} \lambda_s^g \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_{sh}^l}{\partial z^p} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{sh}^l}{\partial \dot{z}^g} \lambda_p^g \right) + (\lambda_{st}^l \lambda_{ph}^t - \lambda_{pt}^l + \lambda_{hs}^t)$$

This tensor H_{phs}^l defined by (3.7) will be called the second curvature tensor depending on the symmetric connection

λ_{hk}^j . There is no possibility of existence of any other curvature tensor, because of the fact that our connection coefficient (2.1) is symmetric in its lower indices.

Moreover, considering the inegrability condition of the starred counterpart of equation (2.2) we find two more curvature tensors, which are

$$H_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*} = \frac{\partial \lambda_{m^*k^*}^{t^*}}{\partial z^r} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{m^*k^*}^{t^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^s} \lambda_r^s$$

and

$$H_{p^*h^*s^*}^{l^*} = \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_{p^*h^*}^{l^*}}{\partial z^{s^*}} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{p^*h^*}^{l^*} \lambda_{s^*}^{g^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^{g^*}} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \lambda_{s^*h^*}^{l^*}}{\partial z^{p^*}} - \frac{\partial \lambda_{s^*h^*}^{l^*} \lambda_{p^*}^{g^*}}{\partial \dot{z}^{g^*}} \right) + (\lambda_{p^*t^*}^{l^*} \lambda_{h^*s^*}^{t^*} - \lambda_{s^*t^*}^{l^*} \lambda_{p^*h^*}^{t^*})$$

In fact, these tensors are starred counterparts of (3.4) and (3.7) respectively. From equations (3.4) and (3.8) we immediately infer the following:

Theorem (3.1) If the connection coefficient Λ_{ph}^l of our complex manifold are holomorphic functions of z^k and \bar{z}^k , the curvature tensor (3.4) vanishes identically.

Theorem (3.2) If the connection coefficient $\Lambda_{p^*h^*}^{l^*}$ of our complex manifold are holomorphic functions of z^{k^*} and \bar{z}^{k^*} , the curvature tensor (3.8) vanishes identically.

Substituting from (2.1) (a) and (2.9) (b) in (3.4) and making use of (1.12), (1.13), (1.16) and (2.1)(a) we get

$$H_{mkr}^t = K_{mkr}^t + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_{km|r}^t + \frac{\partial \Lambda_{km}^t}{\partial z^s} \Omega_{a^*r}^s \cdot \dot{z}^{a^*} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

which in view of (2.6) reduces to the form

$$H_{mkr}^t = K_{mkr}^t + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_{km;r}^t + \frac{\partial \Gamma_{km}^t}{\partial z^s} \Omega_{a^*r}^s \cdot \dot{z}^{a^*} \right) \quad (3.11)$$

Thus, we have

Theorem (3.3) the first curvature tensor H_{mkr}^t depending on the symmetric connection coefficients Λ_{hk}^j and the curvature tensor K_{mkr}^t are related by the education (3.10) or equivalently by (3.11).

Again if we start from the equation (3.8) and proceed in a way similar to above then we find that

$$H_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*} = K_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_{k^*m^*|r}^{t^*} + \frac{\partial \Lambda_{k^*m^*}^{t^*}}{\partial \bar{z}^s} \Omega_{ar}^s \dot{z}^a \right) \quad (3.12)$$

and

$$H_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*} = K_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_{k^*m^*;r}^{t^*} + \frac{\partial \Gamma_{k^*m^*}^{t^*}}{\partial \bar{z}^s} \Omega_{ar}^s \dot{z}^a \right) \quad (3.13)$$

which lead us to the following :

Theorem (3.4) the starred counterpart $H_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*}$ for the first curvature tensor H_{mkr}^t depending on the systemic connection coefficient $\Lambda_{h^*k^*}^{j^*}$ and the curvature tensor $K_{m^*k^*r}^{t^*}$ are related by the equation (3.12) or equivalently by (3.13).

Our next step is to establish a relationship in between the curvature tensor H_{hps}^l , K_{hps}^l and \bar{K}_{hps}^l .

Substituting in (3.7) from (2.1) (a) and (2.9) (a) and making use of (1.12), (1.13), (1.14) and (2.1) (a) we find

$$H_{hps}^l = \frac{1}{2} (K_{hps}^l + \bar{K}_{hps}^l) + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{2} (\Omega_{st}^l \Omega_{hp} + \Omega_{sh}^l \Omega_{pt}) - \left(\Omega_{sa}^l \frac{\partial \Lambda_{ph}^l}{\partial z^a} + \Omega_{pa}^l \frac{\partial \Lambda_{sh}^l}{\partial z^a} \right) \dot{z}^a \right] \quad (3.14)$$

Similarly substituting in (3.9) from (2.1) (b) and (2.9) (b) and simplifying with the help of (1.12) and starred counterpart of (1.14) and (1.5) we find

$$H_{h^*p^*s^*}^{l^*} = \frac{1}{2} (K_{h^*p^*s^*}^{l^*} + \bar{K}_{h^*p^*s^*}^{l^*}) + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{2} (\Omega_{s^*t^*}^{l^*} \Omega_{h^*p^*} + \Omega_{s^*h^*}^{l^*} \Omega_{p^*t^*}^{l^*}) - \left(\Omega_{s^*a^*}^{l^*} \frac{\partial \Lambda_{p^*h^*}^{l^*}}{\partial \bar{z}^a} + \Omega_{p^*a^*}^{l^*} \frac{\partial \Lambda_{s^*h^*}^{l^*}}{\partial \bar{z}^a} \right) \dot{z}^{a^*} \right] \quad (3.15)$$

Thus we have the following theorems :

Theorem (3.5) the second curvature tensor H_{hps}^l depending on the symmetric connection coefficients Λ_{hk}^j and the curvature tensors K_{hps}^l , \bar{K}_{hps}^l are related by the equation (3.14).

Theorem (3.6) The starred counterpart of the second curvature tensor H_{hps}^l depending on the symmetric connection coefficients $\Lambda_{h^*k^*}^{j^*}$ and the curvature tensors $K_{h^*p^*s^*}^{l^*}$, $\bar{K}_{h^*p^*s^*}^{l^*}$ are related by the equations (3.15)

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